

SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCES OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PHYSICAL ACTIVITY DURING PREGNANCY AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES

Ana Karina Marques Salge*, Marília Cordeiro de Souza*, Raphaela Maioni Xavier*, Thaila Correa Castral*, Karina Machado Siqueira*, Renata Calciolari Rossi*, Janaina Valadares Guimarães*, Pedro Teixeira Meireles**, Bruno Belmonte Martineli Gomes[□], George Kemil Abdalla^{□□} and Douglas Reis Abdalla^{◇,1}

*Faculty of Nursing, Federal University of Goiás, Goiânia, GO, Brazil., **Medicine Course, University of Uberaba, Uberaba, MG, Brazil., [□]Biomedicine, University of São Paulo, Ribeirão Preto, SP, Brazil., ^{□□}Health Sciences, Faculty of Human Talents, Uberaba, MG, Brazil., [◇]Health Sciences, Faculty of Human Talents and University of Uberaba, Uberaba, MG, Brazil.

ABSTRACT During the gestational period, depending on the nutritional needs, the anabolic state remains dynamic, making continuous adaptations about several macros and micronutrients. The practise of physical exercises during pregnancy has become a current theme in the scientific community because it makes an influence on the maternal-infant outcome. An integrative review of the literature aimed at identifying the relationship between physical activity during pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. A survey was conducted on the electronic databases BVS, Scielo, and PubMed. Had been selected 08 studies from 2006 to 2017, in Portuguese, available in full-text online, published in Portuguese, English and Spanish. The practice of continuous and well-directed physical exercise brings innumerable benefits to the mother-child binomial, with favourable neonatal outcomes, for example, reduction of birth weight, adequate birth weight for gestational dyad, term deliveries and prevention of childhood obesity. However, some studies have found an increase in birth weight in infants of women who exercised at low intensities. The inconsistency in the components of physical activity, such as intensity, frequency and duration about the outcomes at birth, still need more investigations. It is concluded that there is a need for more studies on neonatal outcomes in relation to the practice of physical activity during the gestational period, as well as more information about the ways to stimulate the pregnant women to practice regular physical activity and guided by the professionals that take care of her during the prenatal and postpartum.

KEYWORDS pregnancy, pregnant, exercise, physical activity, physical exercise, motor activity

Introduction

During the gestational period, depending on the nutritional needs, the anabolic state remains dynamic, making continuous

adaptations about several macro and micronutrients. Comparing the first and the last stage of gestation, in the first the weight gain is reduced, for this reason needing to be continuously controlled to avoid deficiency or excess. Excessive weight gain may expose pregnant women to several complications, including in childbirth and the puerperal period[1]. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) identifies that the practice of regular physical activity, during the gestational period, can aid in the control of weight gain during pregnancy and postpartum, especially when nutritional support is adequate[2].

For years, pregnant women were advised to decrease their activities or even interrupt occupational work, especially during late pregnancy, because it was believed that exercise could

Copyright © 2019 by the International Sci Ink Press Ltd
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.physical-activity-pregnancy
First Received: July 23, 2019
Accepted: August 02, 2019
Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹Health Sciences, Faculty of Human Talents and University of Uberaba, Uberaba, MG, Brazil.; Email: drabdalla@facthus.edu.br

increase the risk of preterm labour through stimulation of uterine activity[3]. Currently, the body is cultured, and there is an aversion to obesity, so it is increasingly required of the pregnant woman, whenever possible, an active life[4].

The practise of physical exercises during pregnancy has become a theme discussed in the scientific community. In addition to exerting influence on the recommended maternal weight gain and fetal growth, its practice is associated with the prevention and control of several diseases, such as diabetes and Gestational Hypertensive Disease (DHG). This because provide beneficial effects on gestational outcomes, the sensation of well-being, improvement of fatigue, quality of sleep, back pain, glycemic control in diabetic pregnant women, that is, resulting in a better quality of life for pregnant women [3,5,6,7].

Moreover, the practice of physical activity during pregnancy is associated with the reduction of complications, such as excess and low gestational weight, cesarean deliveries, pre-eclampsia and gestational diabetes [8,9,10,11].

The ACOG (2002), in the mid-1990s, identified that regular physical activity during pregnancy could be performed as long as the pregnant woman presents the appropriate conditions for this. However, there are still insufficient published studies focusing on the practice of regular physical activity during pregnancy, as well as information on its indication[12,6]. Furthermore, there are some controversial about neonatal outcomes in the sense that the physical activity during pregnancy may influence the birth weight of the newborn at birth, type of delivery, as well as Apgar score[13]. Given this context, the present study wants to evaluate the available evidence in the scientific literature on the relationship between physical activity during pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

Methods

The integrative review consists of research that allows evaluation and synthesis of evidence, as well as knowledge about the phenomenon, studied, to produce an overview of complex concepts, theories or relevant health problems, from pre-existing studies, proposing effective interventions in health care [14,15]. For this, the present study was carried out in 6 methodological stages. The first stage consisted of the elaboration of the hypothesis of the research, that is, the problem identified, the search engine presented, and the descriptors or key words described. In the second step, it established what it is the criteria of inclusion and exclusion of the articles to be selected for a sample composition. The third stage consisted of the exploratory reading of the titles and abstracts of the articles for pre-selection. The analytical reading of the articles to compile, analyze and categorize the information composed the fourth stage. In the fifth stage, the results were interpreted. And in the last stage, effected the synthesis of the results and presented them, which permeate the guiding question [16].

Therefore, it was decided to perform a search on the concepts: physical activity, gestation and perinatal outcomes. From these concepts, the guiding question was defined: what scientific evidence is available in the literature on the relationship between physical activity during pregnancy and neonatal outcomes?

After formulating the question to be researched, a bibliographic survey was carried out on the platforms: Biblioteca Virtual em Saúde (BVS), in the Lilacs databases (Latin American and Caribbean Literature in Health Sciences / Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences), Scielo Library and PubMed. About the search of the descriptors, the structured and trilingual

vocabulary DeCS (Descritores em Ciências da Saúde), available in BVS.

The lifting of data conducted between June 25 and August 15, 2017. The selection of the texts proceeded with the searches on the platforms, using the filters available for texts published between 2006 and 2017. For the selection of publications, the criteria of inclusion were: scientific articles, published in Portuguese, English and Spanish, between the years 2006 to 2017, available online and the free full text. Articles without abstract in databases or incomplete, editorials, letters to the editor, reflective studies, systematic or integrative reviews of the literature were excluded.

After defining the guiding question, locating and selecting the articles, 374 potentially eligible publications were identified for inclusion in this review. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the sample consisted of 135 publications, after the withdrawal of the duplicate records (15), the summaries of 120 records were analyzed to verify if they met the eligibility criteria and if they answered the question that guides. This review excluded 94 records. In 94, only 26 were analyzed in full to confirm the eligibility for quantitative synthesis of data, remaining eight articles for synthesis and analysis of the data according to the flowchart of a selection of the publications below (Flowchart 1).

After the exploratory reading and selection of the material, the analytical reading was propitiated by reading the selected works, which enabled the organization of ideas in order of importance and subsequent fixation. After the analytical reading, started the interpretive reading that dealt with the comment made by the linkage of the obtained data, with emphasis on the main ideas. Finally, the presented data were submitted to content analysis and a synthesis of the knowledge was made for the construction of the final article.

Results and Discussion

Of the 08 articles that composed the sample, seven were in the English language (87.5%) and only one (12.5%) in the Portuguese language. It was observed that in 2011, 2014 and 2017 there was only one publication (12.5%) each, whereas in 2013 there were two publications (25%), and in 2012 three publications were identified (37.5%).

As for the countries, of the eight articles, one (12.5%) was produced in Brazil in the state of Rio Grande do Sul. The remaining seven articles were produced outside Brazil; one was produced in Canada (12.5%), one in Iran (12.5%), one in Norway (12.5%) and four in the United States (50%). The publications are described in Table 1, classified according to the year of publication.

Recently, the topic of physical activity during pregnancy has been focused on debates in the scientific community because it has several benefits and reaches different areas of the maternal organism. On the other hand, lack of regular physical activity is one of the factors associated with the greater susceptibility of exposure to diseases such as depression, obesity, diabetes and hypertension, during and after gestation [25]. Therefore, the practice of physical activity can provide beneficial effects on maternal-infant outcomes [26,27].

The ACOG recommends exercise at least three times a week during pregnancy to increase fitness and maternal well-being. It refers that the physical activity developed during pregnancy should consider regular and moderate-intensity exercises, according to gestational age, activities centred on the health conditions of the pregnant woman, the experience in practising

Figure 1 Flowchart of Selection of Publications

Table 1: Distribution of studies concerning the relationship between physical activity during pregnancy and neonatal outcomes, according to study identification (title and periodical), authors, year of publication, type of study, objectives and main results.

Study identification (title, periodical)	Authors	Year of publication	Type of study	Objectives	Main results
Relationship between Daily Physical Activity During the Last Month of Pregnancy and Pregnancy Outcome/Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal	Jahromi MK, Jahromi BN, Hojjati S	2011	Transversal study	Evaluate the relationship between daily physical activities as biomechanical load and energy expenditure and physical exercise during domestic activities with birth weight, type of delivery, and Apgar score.	There was no relationship between biomechanical load and energy and birth weight. There was a correlation between Apgar, biomechanics and energy load, that is, newborns of mothers who practised physical activity before or during pregnancy had a greater weight than the group that did not practice physical activity. The Apgar score did not indicate significant results in either group. It is possible to conclude that daily activities in the normal range do not induce any harmful effects on birth weight. However, physical activity before and during pregnancy can have a positive effect on birth weight.
Leisure-time Physical Activity in Pregnancy and the Birth Weight Distribution: Where is the effect?/J Phys Act Health.	Mudd LM, Pivarnik J, Holzman CB, Paneth N, Pfeiffer K, Chung H	2012	Retrospective/prospective study	Characterize the effect of leisure physical activity and the weight of the newborn at birth.	The practice of physical activity at leisure or above-recommended levels during the gestational period indicates that there may be a reduction in the weight of the newborn at birth. For this reason, future studies should be carried out to detail physical leisure activities during each trimester of pregnancy to test and improve the results found in several populations of pregnant women.
Atividade física durante a gestação e associação com indicadores de saúde materno infantil/Rev Saúde Pública	Dumith SC, Domingues MR, Mendoza-Sassi RA, Cesar JÁ.	2012	Transversal study	Analyze factors associated with the practice of physical activity during gestation and its relationship with maternal and child health indicators.	Women who practiced physical activity during pregnancy showed a lower probability of having a cesarean section and having a stillborn child. There was no relationship between physical activity and preterm birth, hospitalization and low birth weight.

<p>A prospective study of the association between vigorous physical activity during pregnancy and length of gestation and birthweight/Matern Child Health J.</p>	<p>Jukic AMZ, Evenson KR, Daniels JL, Herring AH, Wilcox AJ Hartmann KE</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>Clinical investigation</p>	<p>Examine the correlation between vigorous physical activity during pregnancy and duration of gestation and birth weight.</p>	<p>The recreational activity was associated with prolonged gestation. The higher frequency of vigorous recreational activity was associated with reduced preterm labour (≥ 4 sessions per week compared to none or once per week). Birth weight was not associated with physical activity. For these reasons, future studies should be conducted to investigate the components of physical activity (i.e., intensity, duration and frequency) about birth outcomes.</p>
<p>Physical activity during pregnancy and language development in the offspring/Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.</p>	<p>Jukic AMZ, Lawlor DA, Juhl M, Katrine M. Owe KM, Lewis B, Liu J, Wilcox AJ, Longnecker MP.</p>	<p>2013</p>	<p>Longitudinal study</p>	<p>Investigate the relationship between maternal physical activity during pregnancy and language development.</p>	<p>The children of women who practised physical activity when compared to pregnant women who did not perform physical activity during pregnancy were more likely to score higher on the Mac Arthur scores at 15 months. However, they also identified that high levels of general physical activity were associated with lower verbal IQ in children at eight years of age. It is important to note that general activity may include occupation, family and leisure activities, as well as chemical exposures, stress or alternative work (cited by nursing) that can influence language development. The most robust finding was the transient increase in the vocabulary of the descendants of young women who practised physical activity during pregnancy. Further comparative studies are needed.</p>
<p>Prepregnancy Physical Activity about Offspring Birth Weight: A Prospective Population-Based Study in Norway—The HUNT Study/Journal of Pregnancy</p>	<p>Krogsgaard S, Gudmundsdottir, SL, Nilsen TIL.</p>	<p>2013</p>	<p>Transversal study</p>	<p>Examine the relationship between physical exercise during pregnancy and birth weight of the offspring and to evaluate the combined association of pre-gestational body mass index (BMI) and physical exercise on birth weight.</p>	<p>There was no clear relationship between exercise and activity time. Women who reported no physical exercise reduced the risk of a macrosomic child compared to women who had a high level of exercise. Excess weight (BMI ≥ 25.0 kg / m²) was positively associated with birth weight and risk of macrosomia only among the less active women.</p>

<p>23. Linking Nontraditional Physical Activity and Preterm Delivery in Urban African-American Women/Women's Health Issues.</p>	<p>Sealy-Jefferson S, Hegner K, Misra DP.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>Retrospective/prospective study</p>	<p>Examine the relationships between preterm birth and intensity and duration of physical activity and not physical activity practitioners, such as climbing and walking, during pregnancy.</p>	<p>The rate of preterm birth was 16.7% (n = 832). The results suggested a significant decrease in the prevalence of preterm birth for women who walked longer than 30 min/day, associated with one purpose (less stressful behaviours, drug use and smoking) compared to women who walked less than or equal to at 30 min/day. Therefore, the results suggest that moving to a purpose during pregnancy may confer protection against preterm birth among low-income urban African American women.</p>
<p>Physical activity during pregnancy and infant's birth weight: results from the 3D Birth Cohort/BMJ Open Sport Exerc Med</p>	<p>Bisson M, Croteau J, Guinhouya BC, Bujold E, Audibert F, Frase WD, Marc I</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>Cohort study</p>	<p>Evaluate the association between maternal physical activity and the birth weight of the newborn or risk of inappropriate weight for gestational age.</p>	<p>Pregnant women who do intense sports and practice physical activity in the first trimester had a newborn with lower birth weight. Also, other suggested evidence is that the first trimester may be a sensitive period for fetal growth programming, the greater the weight gain at the onset of gestation, the greater the probability of overweight in the neonatal period and infancy. Despite reducing birth weight, sports and physical activity during the first trimester were not associated with an increased risk of underweight for gestational age.</p>

physical exercises and the demonstration of interest and necessity of the pregnancy[2].

Fetal development and growth may be influenced positively or negatively by the maternal environment. Studies by Hatch et al. (1993) with a cohort of 800 pregnant women that were distributed in three groups according to the intensity of physical activity (mild, moderate and practically high and non-practicing intensity) observed that pregnant women who practised physical activity throughout the three gestational trimesters tended to have a newborn with greater weight. A clinical study involving 46 pregnant women presented similar results in previously sedentary pregnant women, whose objective was to evaluate the impact of physical activity on birth weight. And the pregnant women who practised exercise more frequently at the beginning of gestation had newborns with higher birth weight[?].

Others studies that analyzed the regular practice of exercise found an association with fetal growth, with a consequent increase in birth weight in newborns of women who practised exercise with low intensity, with an increase in weight equal to 97 g and 86 g in the second and third respectively [4,24,15].

However, women who practice sports and physical activity during the first trimester of pregnancy may present favourable neonatal outcomes such as adequate weight and reduced birth weight at birth [17,18], significant reduction of newborn GIG [24,22], possibly due to increased insulin sensibility [28,29], increased vocabulary and higher scores on Mac Arthur scores at 15 months[21]. Physical activity at the onset of gestation may also influence the body composition of the newborn with a long-term beneficial impact of childhood obesity prevention [24,30].

It was also believed that the practice of physical activity during gestation could stimulate uterine contraction, promoting the anticipation of labour. However, there seems to be a consensus that the practice of physical activity monitored during pregnancy does not contribute to prematurity [23]. It is known that regular physical activity strengthens the pelvic muscles, being one more factor in providing term births [3,19].

Therefore, women who practice vigorous physical activity tend to have a lower probability of preterm birth [22]. The results suggest that there are protective effects of exercise or that perhaps premature births can intervene in active physical development, possibly because behind this mechanism is the increased insulin sensibility caused by exercise that results in the decreased inflammatory process, a risk factor for premature birth [31].

The practice of physical exercise carries potential risks to the fetus in situations where exercise intensity is very high. This creates a state of hypoxia for the fetus, in situations where there is a risk of abdominal trauma, in situations of hyperthermia of the pregnant woman, redistribution of the blood volume to the muscles, thus stealing volume of the uterine territory and may also be related to the changes of the beats fetal heart disease (BCF). These factors can generate fetal stress, intrauterine growth restriction and prematurity [4,24,15].

However, the ACOG recommends the practice of regular physical exercise for pregnant women, including sedentary women, seeing that the benefits are global, including improvements in mental health, whereas pregnancy is a period of intense physical and emotional changes [31].

The study by Batista et al. (2003) and Dumith et al. (2012) demonstrated that the participation of pregnant women in physical exercises, especially in the first two trimesters, was effectively associated with the lower risk of cesarean sections. And, while

physical activity during pregnancy reduces labour pains, helping physically active pregnant women to tolerate better labour, especially the longer ones, than those who are not trained or those who exercise only sporadically.

The recommendations of the ACOG and the Department of Health and Human Services are to encourage physical exercise and recommendation of physical activity, respectively. However, there is considerable variability in the literature about how to recommend activity during pregnancy so that it may have favourable neonatal outcomes and benefits, considering that there are several inconsistent conclusions regarding intensity and frequency [2,20].

Conclusion

It is essential to emphasize the need to stimulate pregnant women to practice regular and oriented physical activity since this entails innumerable benefits on pregnant and newborn health. However, professionals responsible for prenatal and postpartum care should be adequately trained for this action. The aspire is that physical activities occur with planning, follow-up and systematization aiming at the favourable neonatal outcome, such as reduction of birth weight, adequate birth weight for gestational dyad, term deliveries and prevention of childhood obesity.

It wasn't found in the reviewed literature any type of standardization of activity recommended by specialized organs. The reduced number of studies regarding neonatal outcomes and practice of physical exercises during pregnancy makes it impossible for the scientific research professionals that approach the subject to perform better. New studies will be of great value for guidelines on systematized physical activity during pregnancy with the birth of a healthy newborn.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

Funding

None.

References

1. Rössner S. Physical activity and prevention and treatment of weight gain associated with pregnancy: current evidence and research issues. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*, United States 1999;31 Suppl 4: 560-563.
2. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG]. Exercise during pregnancy and the postpartum period. *Am Col Obstet Gyneco*, Washington 2002;99:171-173.
3. Batista DC, Chiara VL, Gugelmin SA, Martins PD. Atividade física e gestação: saúde da gestante não atleta e crescimento fetal. *Rev Bras Saúde Matern Infant*. Recife 2003;3(2):151-158.
4. Dertkigil MSJ, Cecatti JG, Cavalcante SR, Baciuk EP, Bernardo ANA. Líquido amniótico, atividade física e imersão em água na gestação. *Rev. Bras. Saúde Matern. Infant*, Campinas 2005;5(4):403-410.

5. Larsson L, Lindqvist PG. Low-impact exercise during pregnancy – a study of safety. *Acta Obstet Gynecol*, Malmö 2005;84:34-38.
6. Tavares JS, Melo ASO, Amorim MMR, Barros VO, Benício MHA, Takito MY, Cardoso MAA. Associação entre o padrão de atividade física materna, ganho ponderal gestacional e peso ao nascer em uma coorte de 118 gestantes no município de campina grande, Nordeste do Brasil. *Rev Assoc Med Bras*, São Paulo 2009;55(3):335-341.
7. Ministério da Saúde. Secretaria de Políticos de Saúde. Área Técnica de Saúde da Mulher. Parto, aborto e puerpério: assistência humanizada à mulher/ Ministério da Saúde, Secretaria de Políticas de Saúde, Área Técnica da Mulher. – Brasília: Ministério da Saúde, 2001.
8. Oken E. Associations of physical activity and inactivity before and during pregnancy with glucose tolerance. *Obstet Gynecol*, United States 2006;108(5):1200-1007.
9. Zhang C. A prospective study of pregravid physical activity and sedentary behaviors in relation to the risk for gestational diabetes mellitus. *Arch Intern Med*. Uruguay 2006;166(5):543-548.
10. Dumith SC, Domingues MR, Mendoza RA, Cesar JA. Atividade física durante a gestação e associação com indicadores de saúde materno-infantil. *Rev Saúde Pública*, Rio Grande do Sul 2012;46(2):327-333.
11. Artal R, Gardin SK. Perspectiva histórica. In: Artal R, Wiswell AR, Drinkwater LR. editor. *O exercício na gravidez*. São Paulo: Manole, 1999. P.1-7.
12. Smith KM, Campbell CG. Aerobic exercise training during pregnancy reduces depressive symptoms in nulliparous women: a randomised trial. *Journal of Physiotherapy* 2013;2013.
13. Godfrey KM, Barker DJ. Fetal nutrition and adult disease. *Am Clin Nutr* 2000;71:1344S-52S.
14. Whittemore R, Knafl K. The integrative review: updated methodology. *J Adv Nurs*. England 2005;52(5):546-553.
15. Galvão CM, Sawada NO, Trevizan MA. Systematic review: a resource that allows the incorporation of evidence into nursing practice. *Rev Latino-am Enfermagem*. [internet]. 2004 [citado 2017 ago. 10];17(4):758-764. Disponível em: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rlae/v12n3/v12n3a14.pdf>
16. De Sousa LD, Lunardi Filho WD, Lunardi VL, Santos SS, Dos Santos CP. The nursing scientific production about the clinic: an integrative review. *Rev Esc Enferm. USP. (SP)* [Internet]. 2011 [citado 2017 ago 10];45(2):494-500. Disponível em: http://www.scielo.br/pdf/reeusp/v45n2/en_v45n2a26.pdf
17. Koushkie Jahromi M, Namavar Jahromi B, Hojjati S. Relationship between Daily Physical Activity During Last Month of Pregnancy and Pregnancy Outcome. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*. 2011;13(1):15-20.
18. Mudd LM, Pivarnik J, Holzman CB, Paneth N, Pfeiffer K, Chung H. Leisure-time Physical Activity in Pregnancy and the Birth Weight Distribution: Where is the effect? *Journal of physical activity & health*. 2012;9(8):1168-1177.
19. Dumith SC, Domingues MR, Mendoza-Sassi RA, Cesar JÁ. Atividade física durante a gestação e associação com indicadores de saúde materno-infantil. *Rev. Saúde Pública*. 2011; 46(2): 327-333.
20. Jukic AMZ, Evenson KR, Daniels JL, Herring AH, Wilcox AJ, Hartmann KE. A prospective study of the association between vigorous physical activity during pregnancy and length of gestation and birthweight. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*. 2012;16(5):1031-1044.
21. Jukic AMZ, Lawlor DA, Juhl M, et al. Physical activity during pregnancy and language development in the offspring. *Paediatric and perinatal epidemiology*. 2013;27(3):283-293.
22. Krogsgaard S, Gudmundsdottir, SL, Nilsen TIL. Prepregnancy Physical Activity in relation to Offspring Birth Weight: A Prospective Population-Based Study in Norway—The HUNT Study. *Journal of Pregnancy*. 2013;2013:6.
23. Sealy-Jefferson S, Hegner K, Misra DP. Linking Nontraditional Physical Activity and Preterm Delivery in Urban African-American Women. *Women’s health issues: official publication of the Jacobs Institute of Women’s Health*. 2014;24(4):e389-e395.
24. Bisson M, Croteau J, Guinhouya BC, Bujold E, Audibert F, Frase WD, Marc I. Physical activity during pregnancy and infant’s birth weight: results from the 3D Birth Cohort. *BMJ Open Sport Exerc Med* 2017;3:e000242.
25. Smith K.M, Campbell CG. Physical Activity during Pregnancy: Impact of Applying Different Physical Activity Guidelines. *J Pregnancy, Egypt* 2013;2013:6.
26. Lynch KE, Landsbaugh JR, Whitcomb BW, Pekow P, Markenson G, Chasan-Taber L. Physical Activity of Pregnant Hispanic Women. *Am J Prev Med Netherlands* 2012;43(4):434-439.
27. Tendais I, Figueiredo B, Mota J, Conde A. Physical activity, health-related quality of life and depression during pregnancy. *Cad. Saúde Pública São Paulo* 2011;27(2):219-228.
28. Alderman BW, Zhao H, Holt VL, Watts DH, Beresford SSA. Maternal physical activity in pregnancy and infant size for gestational age. *Annals of Epidemiology*. 1998; 8(8): 513-519.
29. Owe KM, Nystad W, Bø K. Association between regular exercise and excessive newborn birth weight. *Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2009 Oct;114(4):770-6
30. Ghodsi Z, Asltoghiri M. Effects of aerobic exercise training on maternal and neonatal outcome: a randomized controlled trial on pregnant women in Iran. *J Pak Med Assoc. Pakistan* 2014;64(9):1053-1056.
31. Harrison CL, Thompson RG, Teede HJ, Lombard CB. Measuring physical activity during pregnancy. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical England Activity*. 2011;8:19.